

Study the Role of Zolendronic Acid (IV Bisphosphonate) Therapy in Providing Good Pain Relief in Fragility Fractures

Sunil Kumar Mooknoor¹, Prathibha H²

¹Consultant, Dept of Orthopedics, Shri Sugureshwar Hospital, Workanalli Road, Near Basaveshwar Gunj Circle, Yadgir -585201 Karnataka India

²Consultant, Dept of Anaesthesia, Shri Sugureshwar Hospital, Workanalli Road, Near Basaveshwar Gunj Circle, Yadgir -585201 Karnataka India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Sunil Kumar Mooknoor

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Abstract:

Background: Osteoporosis is decrease in the overall amount of bone. It is not at all the same as bone decalcification. It is not only prevalent among postmenopausal women but also occurs in men and women with underlying conditions or major risk factors associated with bone demineralization.

Objective: To study the role of Zolendronic acid (IV Bisphosphonate)therapy in providing good pain relief in osteoporotic fragility fractures.

Methods: This Prospective single arm, Observational Cohort Study was conducted among 50 Patients above the age of 40 years of either sex presenting with osteoporotic fracture to Department of Orthopedics St. Martha's Hospital, Nrupathunga road, Bengaluru. Duration of study was December 2015 to December 2017.

Results: In the initial six months, ZA provided significant improvement in back pain as depicted by VAS in patients with VCF. ZA being an IV yearly dose regimen is well accepted and tolerated by the patients compared to other oral bisphosphonates. Febrile reactions, myalgia, minor maculopopular rashes were the adverse effects noted in 2 patients who were symptomatically addressed. No other significant adverse effects noted during the study period in any of the patients. All the patients found excellent clinical improvement in terms of pain in the initial 6 months post infusion. At the end of one year, all the patients were willing for a second dose. This study noted ZA therapy had significant decrease in pain intensity.

Conclusions: ZA being an annual IV dosing regimen has better compliance than other oral bisphosphonates. ZA provides significant improvement in patients backpain in the initial 6 months and also prevents the incidence of new VCF in patients having Osteoporotic VCF.

Keywords: Zolendronic Acid (IV Bisphosphonate) Therapy, Good Pain Relief, Osteoporotic Fragility Fractures.

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Introduction

Osteoporosis affects an enormous number of people, of both sexes and all races, and its prevalence will increase as the population ages. Based on data from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey III (NHANES III), NOF has estimated that more than 10 million Americans have osteoporosis and an additional 33.6 million have low bone density of the hip²¹. About one out of every two Caucasian women will experience an osteoporosis-related fracture at some point in her lifetime, as will approximately one in five men [1].

Osteoporosis-related fractures create a heavy economic burden, causing more than 432,000 hospital admissions, almost 2.5 million medical office visits and about 180,000 nursing home admissions annually in the US [2]. The cost to the

healthcare system associated with osteoporosis-related fractures has been estimated at \$17 billion for 2005; hip fractures account for 14 percent of incident fractures and 72 percent of fracture costs [3]. Due to the aging population, the Surgeon General estimates that the number of hip fractures and their associated costs could double or triple by the year 2040.

In a study among Indian women aged 30-60 years from low-income groups, bone mineral density (BMD) at all skeletal sites was much lower than values reported from developed countries, with a high prevalence of osteopenia (52%) and osteoporosis (29%), thought to be due to inadequate nutrition [4]. In a more recent study from Delhi, 792 males and 808 postmenopausal females with a mean age of 57.67 ± 9.46 years

were evaluated. Osteoporosis was present in 35.1% of subjects (M-24.6%, F-42.5%) and osteopenia in 49.5% (M-54.3%, F-44.9%) [5]. Osteoporosis at the spine and hip was present in 42.7% and 11.4% subjects using the Hologic database and in 27.7% and 8.3% subjects using the ICMR database [6].

Widespread vitamin D deficiency has been shown unequivocally across all ages throughout India. More than 80% of urban Indians have serum 25(OH) D levels below 20 ng/ml. Studies indicate approximately 80-90% of hip fracture patients are vitamin D deficient [7,8].

ZA is a potent bisphosphonate with intravenous administration regimens (once yearly IV). It is a nitrogen containing bisphosphonate and hence also inhibits protein prenylation, one of the end products in the mevalonic acid pathway, by inhibition of the enzyme farnesyl pyrophosphate synthase. This effect disrupts intracellular protein trafficking and may ultimately lead to apoptosis.

Materials and Methods

This Prospective single arm, Observational Cohort Study was conducted among Patients above the age of 40 years of either sex presenting with osteoporotic fracture to Department of Orthopedics St. Martha's Hospital, Nrupathunga road, Bengaluru. Duration of study was December 2015 to December 2017.

Sample Size: It is a hospital based study of 50 cases or more who are fulfilling the Inclusion/Exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria:

Patients of Osteoporotic fragility fracture either sex aged 40 years and above.

All Patients with BMD T score less than -2.5.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients with renal disease
2. Patients with severe cardiac disease
3. Patients on hormone replacement therapy, oral bisphosphonates or any other active management except calcium and vitamin D.
4. Patients with Clinically detectable underlying causes for back pain like primary and or secondary tumors of bone, disc Prolapse, infection, other hormonal abnormalities.
5. Patients with clinically detectable abdominal visceral malignancy.

Investigations

1. Complete blood count
2. Bleeding and clotting times
3. Random Blood Sugar
4. Serum Creatinine and Urea
5. Electrocardiogram
6. Serum calcium and phosphate

7. X ray of area of interest.
8. Bone Mineral Density using DXA AP spine and Lateral vertebral analysis.

Method of collection of data: Patients presenting with fractures in compliance with the criterion of the study population were selected. Informed consent was taken from the patients who agree to be part of the study. Demographic data, History, Clinical examination and details of investigations were recorded in the study Proforma. The assessment tools used are the routine blood investigations, serum calcium, serum alkaline phosphatase, radiographs, USG abdomen, DXA and MRI (only in select cases), severity of pain was recorded as per VAS score. The BMD measurements for the diagnosis of osteoporosis are considered according to WHO and the National Osteoporosis Foundation (NOF) guidelines 2013.

The patients who turned out to be osteoporotic were advised to take sufficient oral fluids for hydration. Later they were given 5mg of ZA IV over a minimum period of 15 min after taking consent and observed for allergic and other reactions for a day. They were advised prophylactic antipyretic medications with paracetamol along with other management for their fracture, along with calcium and vitamin D supplements.

They were assessed after 12 weeks/3 months, 24 weeks/6 months, and one year clinically, radiologically and DEXA scan for BMD at the end of one year. The data were interpreted.

Visit 1/ Day1/ Initial or baseline assessment-

- Screening for inclusion of study and taking informed written consent.
- Details of patient's demographic characteristics, and medical histories, concomitant medications and detailed physical/clinical evaluation were recorded.
- Routine investigations like Complete blood picture, Renal function tests, serum calcium, phosphate, alkaline phosphatase, radiograph, Bone mineral density using DXA were recorded, VAS score was recorded.
- Eligible patients were administered 5mg intravenous ZA with their consent.
- They were observed for any acute reactions for one day, either on OPD basis or in patient if needed

Visit 2/ Week 12-

- Assessment of pain by VAS scale
- All observed or spontaneously volunteered adverse events were recorded.
- Pulse rate and blood pressure were recorded.

Visit 3/ Week 24 -

- Patients improvement with respect to pain were assessed using VAS scale

- All observed or spontaneously volunteered adverse events were recorded.
- Pulse rate and blood pressure were recorded.
- Visit 4/ 1 year-
- Patients improvement with respect to pain were assessed using VAS scale
- All observed adverse events were recorded.
- Pulse rate and blood pressure were recorded.
- Patient's improvement with respect to Bone mineral density was recorded using DXA.

Descriptive and inferential statistical analysis has been carried out in the present study. Results on continuous measurements are presented on Mean±SD (Min-Max) and results on categorical measurements are presented in Numbers (%). Significance is assessed at 5% level of significance. The following assumptions on data is made, **Assumptions:** 1. Dependent variables should be normally distributed, 2. Samples drawn from the population should be random, Cases of the samples should be independent

Student t test (two tailed, dependent) has been used to find the significance of study parameters on continuous scale with in each group.

Significant figures

- Suggestive significance (P value: 0.05 - P <0.10)
- Moderately significant (P value:0.01 - P < 0.05)
- Strongly significant (P value: P 0.01)

Statistical software: The Statistical software namely SAS 9.2, SPSS 15.0, Stata 10.1, MedCalc 9.0.1, Systat 12.0 and R environment ver.2.11.1 were used for the analysis of the data and Microsoft word and Excel have been used to generate graphs, tables etc.

Results:

The comparison from baseline for BMD is using a paired 't' test and for VAS is a Wilcoxon sign rank test.

Table 1: Paired t test

Variables	Mean difference	95% CI	P-value
Initial BMD vs BMD at 1 year	-0.01	(-0.023,-0.003)	0.01
Initial VAS score vs VAS score at 12 weeks	2.86	(2.27,3.45)	<0.001
Initial VAS score vs VAS score at 24 weeks	3.54	(2.95,4.13)	<0.001
Initial VAS score vs VAS score at 1 year	4.19	(3.50,4.88)	<0.001

Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA): There is no statistical significant difference in "BMD at 1 year" between the groups (Surgical & Conservative) when adjusted for "Initial BMD" (P-value >0.05).

Table 2: Comparison of group

Variables	Mean (SD)	Mean difference	95% CI	P-value
Initial BMD				
• Surgical	0.60(0.12)	-0.11	(-0.18,-0.05)	<0.001
• Conservative	0.71(0.08)			
BMD at 1 year				
• Surgical	0.62(0.11)	-0.09	(-0.17,-0.06)	0.002
• Conservative	0.71(0.08)			

Table 3: Summary statistics

Variables	N=50 Mean (SD)
Age	73.4(10.5)
Initial BMD	0.65(0.12)
BMD at 1 year	0.66(0.11)
Initial VAS score	8.3(0.8)
VAS score at 12 weeks	5.4(1.7)
VAS score at 24 weeks	4.7(1.7)
VAS score at 1 year	4.1(2.0)
Sex	
• Female	48(96%)
• Male	2(4%)
Management	
• Conservative	21(42%)
• Surgical	29(58%)

Discussion

A total of 50 patients were selected into the study. In the initial six months, ZA provided significant improvement in back pain as depicted by VAS in patients with VCF. ZA being an IV yearly dose regimen is well accepted and tolerated by the patients compared to other oral bisphosphonates. Febrile reactions, myalgia, minor maculopopular rashes were the adverse effects noted in 2 patients who were symptomatically addressed.

No other significant adverse effects noted during the study period in any of the patients. All the patients found excellent clinical improvement in terms of pain in the initial 6 months post infusion. At the end of one year, all the patients were willing for a second dose. This study noted ZA has significant improvements in Bone mineral density.

Conclusion

Back pain due to Vertebral Osteoporosis appears to be common entity even at the age of 40 years, which is greatly overlooked and under treated.

There is a paucity of Indian studies regarding early diagnosis and management of Osteoporosis and its related complications. This study was an effort to estimate the burden of Vertebral Osteoporosis in patients with backache and patients presenting with fracture following trivial fall and also the effect of annual infusion of ZA on clinical, and laboratory outcomes in such patients.

ZA being an annual IV dosing regimen has better compliance than other oral bisphosphonates. ZA provides significant improvement in patients backpain in the initial 6 months and also prevents the incidence of new VCF in patients having Osteoporotic VCF

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